

IMPACT OF CLOUDIFICATION OF CORPORATE SYSTEMS ON BUSINESS MODELS AND DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES OF COMPANIES

Verner Dmytro

master's degree, V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University

Abstract

The article examines the impact of cloudification of corporate systems on business models and strategies of companies in a rapidly changing technological landscape. Cloudification, understood as the transition to cloud platforms, enables significant cost reduction, increased flexibility, and accelerated innovation. The focus is on analyzing successful cases of cloud technology implementation and their impact on value creation for customers and competitive advantages. The study emphasizes the importance of a strategic approach to cloud technologies for achieving sustainable growth and efficiency in modern business conditions.

Keywords: cloudification, business models, strategies, cloud technologies, innovations.

Introduction

Modern companies face the necessity of constant adaptation to changes in a technological environment that is becoming increasingly dynamic. Cloudification is the process of transitioning corporate systems, applications, data, and IT infrastructure to cloud platforms. This transition to cloud platforms for managing data, resources, and processes provides businesses with a wide range of opportunities: from cost reduction to increased flexibility and speed of innovation implementation. This technological phenomenon not only changes the internal processes of companies but also has a significant impact on their business models and development strategies.

The aim of this study is to investigate the impact of cloudification on the development of business models and strategies of companies across various industries. Particular attention is given to the analysis of successful cloud use cases, as well as the comparison of theoretical models with real business examples.

Main part. Cloudification as a technological driver and its impact on business models

Cloud technologies (CT) are transforming traditional approaches to data management, production processes, and customer interaction. The main process of cloudification is the **migration of infrastructure**, applications, and data to the cloud, allowing companies to save on capital expenditures while focusing on operational costs. According to a report by **McKinsey** [1], companies that actively implement CT can achieve savings of up to **47 % on IT infrastructure costs**, as well as enhance the **efficiency of resource utilization**. Although companies are moving more workloads to the cloud, errors in migration coordination led to negative consequences. Data shows that due to this inefficiency, companies, on average, spend 14 % more on migration than planned, and 38 % of companies have delayed migration by more than a quarter (pic. 1).

Pic. 1. Budget for cloud migration vs actual spend on cloud migration, %

Also, a report by **The Hackett Group** [2] indicates that **migrating to the cloud** allows companies to reduce **labor costs by 18-20 %** and lower overall IT expenses by an average of **20-30 % in the first few years** after the transition. The **flexibility of CT** enables companies to respond more quickly to **market changes** and implement new **business solutions**.

The implementation of CT impacts corporate systems and business as a whole. **For example, distributed systems provide data processing and resource management across physical nodes that may be located in different geographical locations.** This contributes to increased **reliability, fault tolerance, and flexibility** of systems, which is critically important for companies operating on a global scale.

In the context of cloudification, **Big Data** becomes an important tool for companies striving for **analytical transformation** of their business processes. It refers to vast datasets characterized by high generation speed, diverse sources, and significant volumes [3]. Cloud platforms, such as **Google Cloud** or **Microsoft Azure**, provide companies with the ability to store, process, and analyze large datasets using **distributed systems**. These capabilities enable businesses to derive valuable insights in real-time, enhancing their ability to make informed, data-driven decisions. Furthermore, the scalability of cloud platforms ensures that as data volumes

grow, companies can efficiently manage and analyze this data without compromising performance or speed.

Distributed systems and Big Data analytics supported by CT shape companies' development strategies, driving them towards more data-driven decision-making processes. This means that decision-making increasingly relies on in-depth data analysis rather than intuitive or subjective assumptions. Visual changes in business strategy based on the experiences of companies can be seen in **table 1**.

Table 1

Changes in companies' strategy policies with and without cloudification [4]

Aspect	Without cloudification	With cloud technologies (cloudification)
Cost structure	High capital expenditures on it infrastructure.	Cost reduction of 20-50 % due to cloud services.
Flexibility	Limited scalability of resources.	High flexibility: ability to scale resources in real-time based on needs.
Deployment speed	Long process for implementing new systems and applications.	Fast deployment of new applications and services, accelerating time-to-market.
Innovation	Reliance on outdated technologies.	Active adoption of innovations and technologies like Big Data and IoT.
Data analysis	Limited data analysis capabilities.	Expanded real-time data analysis capabilities and use of analytics for decision-making.
Project management	Complicated project management dependent on physical infrastructure.	Improved project management using cloud tools and collaboration platforms.
Security	Data vulnerability due to local storage.	Enhanced security and data protection through cloud solutions and automatic updates.

It can be said that **cloudification is not just a technological process**, but a strategic tool that changes companies' approaches to management. Depending on the level of control and management, there are three models of cloud services. **Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS)** provides companies with flexible resources to scale their operations without the need for significant capital investments. Companies can dynamically adjust their capacities based on business needs, reducing risks associated with investments in physical infrastructure [5]. **Software as a Service (SaaS)** provides access to applications over the Internet, eliminating the need for local installation and maintenance. **SaaS** allows companies to cut licensing and support costs while accelerating the deployment of new applications [6]. **Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS)** enables the development and deployment of applications, providing developers with tools for cloud-based work, which also improves flexibility and speeds up the development of new solutions [7].

Cloudification has a significant impact on traditional business models, compelling companies to rethink their approaches to creating and delivering value. A change in the **cost structure** is one of the most evident consequences of cloudification. Companies are transitioning from **capital expenditures (CapEx)** to **operational expenses (OpEx)**, allowing for better cash flow management and reducing financial risks [8].

Another important step in cloudification is creating a value model for customers. Thanks to cloud technologies, companies can offer customers more flexible and scalable solutions, such as subscription or **on-demand models**. This allows for more **customized services**, increasing customer satisfaction and creating new revenue streams. For instance, companies like **Spotify** utilize cloud platforms to deliver content on a subscription basis, enabling them to scale their offerings quickly and attract new customers. Additionally, cloud-based models allow businesses to gather real-time user data and feedback, which can be used to continuously refine and personalize services. This approach not only strengthens customer loyalty but also helps companies stay competitive by rapidly adapting to market demands.

Cloudification also fosters the emergence of new business models based on **resource sharing**. It allows companies to efficiently manage their operations without the need to own significant assets, opening up new opportunities for growth and scalability.

Transformation of growth and development strategies for companies

The implementation of **CT** necessitates significant changes in companies' development strategies. One of the key aspects is the **differentiation strategy**. Through cloudification, companies can **rapidly implement innovations** and offer customers new products

and services, helping them stand out in the market. For example, **Amazon Web Services (AWS)** provides platforms and tools for the quick development and deployment of new solutions, allowing to **reduce time-to-market**.

The **risk management strategy** is also undergoing transformation. CT mitigate risks associated with IT infrastructure management by automating processes, backing up data, and ensuring security. This allows companies to focus on their core business without diverting resources to maintain internal IT systems. Instead of large one-time investments in technology, companies can distribute their expenses over time, reducing financial burden and making the business more resilient to changes.

Cloudification also facilitates changes in **growth and scaling strategies**. The use of CT enables companies to quickly enter new markets and expand their operations without significant investments in infrastructure. This is especially relevant for **startups** and **small businesses**, which can compete with larger players by rapidly adopting cloud solutions. For instance, companies using cloud platforms for **e-commerce** (the process of buying and selling goods and services online) can quickly scale their operations, responding to changes in demand and expanding their presence in various regions.

For utility companies, transforming operations and systems through digital technologies can provide significant benefits, such as reducing operational costs by up to 25 %. Additionally, productivity may increase by 20-40 % in areas such as safety, reliability, customer satisfaction, and regulatory compliance [4].

The comparison between companies that have implemented **cloudification** and those that continue to use traditional systems reveals clear advantages of CT in today's market. Companies utilizing **cloud solutions** demonstrate higher growth rates and greater flexibility in adapting to changes in market conditions. This is particularly important in the context of **global competition** and rapidly evolving technologies.

Companies that remain on traditional IT systems face several challenges, including **high infrastructure maintenance costs**, limited scalability options, and decreased competitiveness. While companies that have adopted CT can quickly respond to changes in the business environment, those adhering to traditional systems often spend more time and resources modernizing their IT solutions.

Conclusion

Cloudification of corporate systems has a profound impact on business models and development strategies, reshaping cost structures and enhancing operational flexibility. By shifting expenses from CapEx to OpEx, companies can reduce investment risks and better manage cash flow, leading to significant savings

in IT infrastructure and operational costs. This transition also allows businesses to dynamically adjust their resources and infrastructure based on real-time needs, improving scalability and competitive positioning in the market.

Additionally, CT foster a culture of innovation by enabling the rapid development and deployment of new products and services. Businesses utilizing cloud platforms benefit from advanced data analytics and artificial intelligence capabilities, which support data-driven strategies and more informed decision-making processes. These capabilities not only streamline operations but also help companies respond swiftly to market demands, thus enhancing growth opportunities and long-term sustainability in a rapidly evolving technological environment.

References

1. Cloud-migration opportunity: Business value grows, but missteps abound / McKinsey&Company // URL: <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/technology-media-and-telecommunications/our-insights/cloud-migration-opportunity-business-value-grows-but-missteps-abound> (date of application: 09.10.2024).
2. Executive Summary: Achieving Digital World Class excellence / The Hackett Group // URL: <https://www.thehackettgroup.com/insights/whats-the-digital-world-class-advantage/> (date of application: 10.10.2024).
3. Uliankina I., Andreeva V. The role of technological innovations and artificial intelligence in improving the energy efficiency of companies // Bulletin of the Voronezh Institute of High Technologies. 2024. Vol. 18. No. 3.
4. Accelerating digital transformations: A playbook for utilities / McKinsey&Company // URL: <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/mckinsey-digital/our-insights/accelerating-digital-transformations-a-playbook-for-utilities#/> (date of application: 13.10.2024)
5. Amani K. Strategies for efficient resource management in federated cloud environments supporting Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) // Journal of Engineering Research. – 2024. – Vol. 12. – № 2. – P. 101-114
6. Excel G. Leading SaaS innovation within U.S. regulatory boundaries: the role of tpms in navigating compliance // Engineering Science & Technology Journal. – 2024. – P. 1372-1385
7. Hidalgo-Crespo J. An exploratory study for product-as-a-service (PaaS) offers development for electrical and electronic equipment // Procedia CIRP. – 2024. – Vol. 122. – P. 521-526
8. Chenglong G. A Review of the Levelized Cost of Wave Energy Based on a Techno-Economic Model // Energies. – 2023. – № 16. – P. 2144.